

Social Media and Digital Economy Evolvement in Nigeria: A Nexus Appraisal

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Abstract

Social media is fast becoming more significant and almost indispensable in all segments of society, with a strong correlation established between the digital growth level and national economic advancement. However, a yawning digital gap between the developed and developing countries, implicitly, minimizes the latter populace's capacity to optimize the existing social media platforms benefits for extensive and inclusive digital economic growth. With the strength of Nigeria which includes a high population, it is doubtful she can explore the digital space potential. Hence, this paper aims to ascertain the realistic tendency between the social media and digital economic growth in Nigeria. Analytical design is adopted for the study and it was found that the country has not fully exploited the benefits at her disposal due to low internet access, overdependent on imported technology depriving her of seizing the inherent strength of social media. The study recommends that the government should intentionally promote ICT, and exploit bilateral and multilateral opportunities for homegrown technology development, amongst others to advance its digital economic frontier.

Keywords: digital economy, social media, technology, ICT, Nigeria.

1.0 Introduction

Social media is fast becoming more significant and almost indispensable in all segments of society. This includes communication, economy, governance, politics, and education – learning and its transmission. It underscores not only the dynamics of the contemporary fast-paced world but the transformation orchestrated by technology as well.

Moreover, the influence of social media such as Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram, and Telegram, amongst others, on national and international socio-economic progression is attracting greater attention day by day at both levels, making the level of engagement and benefits trends a subject of research and discussion by stakeholders. For instance, United Nations Center for Trade and Development (UNCTAD) (2019) reports indicate a yawning digital gap between developed and developing countries, which, implicitly, minimizes the latter populace's capacity to optimize the social media platforms' benefits.

Meanwhile, there is a strong correlation between the digital growth level and national economic advancement (Herman and Oliver, 2022). Therefore, the likelihood of Nigeria as a developing economy leveraging social media for digital economic growth seems bleak. While the digital economy is still evolving globally, Nigeria with over 200 million population (having approximately 30 years half), the largest economy in Africa (with a \$450 billion GDP) (Pantami, 2020), is expected to be among the topmost harvesters of its gains, especially in Africa. Going by Nigeria's strength, can one safely argue that this is the case? Additionally, since the country has 32.9 million subscribers to social media with WhatsApp having the highest (90 million) and projected to grow to 103 million in 2026 (Sasu, 2022), a sizable percentage of its adult population, a strong connection between social media and fast-paced digital economic evolvement alongside its accompanying advantages appears feasible. Hence, this paper aims to ascertain the realistic tendency between the social media and digital economic growth in Nigeria.

The paper is divided into five sections. Following the introduction is the literature review, then the theoretical framework, methodology, the benefits of social media, the strength and weaknesses of the digital economy in Nigeria, and the conclusion and recommendations.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1. The Concept of Social Media

There are diverse definitions of social media in the literature. For instance, Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) define it as “a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content.” The definition reveals salient features of the internet and technology-enabled medium for users of social media but the ideological inclusion implies some are configured to serve or propagate political orientation (perhaps by the national government), appearing as an extreme case of social interaction.

To Manning (2014), social media is a new form of media involving participant interactions, involving digital platforms, which is different from the broadband centralized era of radio or television characterized by the delayed response but that of the interactive age that enables a large-scale interaction. It is noteworthy, from Jennings’s submission, that social media has taken the media business to a real-time interactive level leveraging technology and internet from the traditional broadband transmission. Additionally, it is the global largest connecting medium for either personal or other interaction purposes, making it almost indispensable for a livelihood by global citizens today.

Given the above analysis, social media can be conceived as the latest trending media outlets that incorporate social interface as its core purpose (informing the christening as social media), though serving business or others including even possibly a yet-to-be-known, imagined, or conceived purposes. Nonetheless, the number of existing social media outlets is becoming difficult to number due to the frequent entry of new ones or applications sharing their features. The popular ones appearing to be most engaged globally are Facebook, WhatsApp, TikTok, Twitter, Instagram, Telegrams, LinkedIn, and Youtube, amongst others. Though social media is witnessing the acquisition of the smaller by the bigger ones, such as the buying of WhatsApp and Instagram by Facebook, the potential for a continuous increase in number seems unlikely to abate, making social media a viable platform for spurring and optimizing digital economy largely undoubted. Hence examining its tagging gains is expedient and considered relevant.

2.2 Conceptualizing Digital Economy

The concept of economy encompasses every sector of national production, which is not a new term. But the digital as a qualifying adjective offers a new meaning to the traditional sense of the word ‘economy’. As such, it is a reflection of the fast-evolving global society engineered mainly by technology. Nevertheless, arriving at a consensus definition of the digital economy remains a task making diverse perspectives that underscore technology, internet, consumers, e-commerce and other ancillary terms resonate in most attempts by scholars in conceptualizing its meaning. For instance, UNCTAD (2019), highlighted the core components of technology (computers, telecommunication devices, the internet as enabling infrastructure, mobile applications, payment services, and e-commerce as a platform for its wide usage. In this sense, it seems safer to describe tools employed in driving the digital economy than to narrow its meaning to a confined sense.

Corroborating the submission above, Pantami (2020) defines digital economy as “any aspect of the economy that is based on or driven by digital technologies.” According to Ahmad and Ribarsky, (2018) (cited in Tebepah, 2020), it means coding data and its processes into binary bits readable by computers and capable of being translated into common languages in voice, business, social networks resulting in their digitalization and the economy simultaneously. While Pantami’s (2020) definition reiterates the chief role of technology in digital economic involvement, the place of any aspect seems to limit the scope of its influence, which is etched on virtually all sectors of the national economy including the traditional sector of agriculture. Therefore, no sector can be safely argued to be left out of technological impact today, making e-commerce permeate all sector as well as incorporates wider consumers. Additionally, Ahhmad and Ribarsky’s (2018) submission is instructive as it offers insight into the procedure and activities that actually give birth to the concept of digital economy.

From this background, the digital economy can be defined as the 21st-century economic system enabled by advancement in technological devices, internet and connectivity, and knowledge or skills enhancement of consumers or end-users. It is necessary to state that the national and international extent of economic digitalization cannot be ascertained or forecasted by the rapid emergence of innovative technology and science equipment in this era of artificial intelligence, robotics, cloud, and the Internet of Things. These dimensions seem to transcend the employment of the social media platform to include other online platforms like Microsoft.

3. Theoretical Framework

Social media engagement theory is employed as the anchor for this study. The theory, though new, evolving and an extension of new media theory, was propounded by Praharad and Ramaswamy (2004) with its thrust as the extent users interface with the social media contents which constitute their experience (Di Gandi and Wasco, 2016). Hence, the relevance or impact of social media is determined by the actualization of its purpose through end-user engagement measurable by interaction and features different from understanding their degree of post-engagement satisfaction which seemingly can be determined via survey poll or research.

In relation to this research, the emergence of the digital economy in Nigeria, its popularity, acceptability and festering appear difficult to be isolated from the social media influence and platform. The extensive social network social media create or enable makes it almost indispensable to the actualization of an inclusive digital economy not only in Nigeria but also in any other one, either developed or developing. This makes the theory apt for analytical tools.

4. Methodology

To achieve the objective of this research, an analytical design, allowing a critical examination of secondary data sources to interrogate related issues with the intent of eliciting facts, is adopted. Hence, the design enables critical examination of both the independent and dependent variables of social media and the digital economy respectively alongside their relationship or connection leveraging credible secondary data.

5. Benefits of Social Media

Social media has become many things to many people, transcending only SMS communication channels. Scholars have identified many-sided socio-economic benefits derivable from the usage of these platforms globally. Some of the notable advantages – which are components of the social media economic power - are discussed in this article to situate its effects on Nigeria's emerging digital economic drive in the global context.

i. Aid Recruitment

Specifically, social networking sites (SNSs) allow users to create web-based profiles where individuals can interact, using social media tools. Though initially designed for socializing with friends and family, these networks are fast morphing into an important professional tool, particularly in the field of recruitment. According to Broughton et al. (2021), social media via the SNSs serves two main purposes. The first is as a marketing tool through which job seekers market themselves to potential employers and vice versa and as a screening mechanism for employers to transmit information cheaply and easily to gain a broader image, far-reaching than that of the traditional recruitment mediums such as print (national dailies) or electronic media. In this sense, job advertisements would attract job seekers across the world, widening opportunities, easing migration, and contributing to foreign earnings accruable to countries, especially developing states like Nigeria.

Corroborating the recruitment advantages of social media, Koch and Gerber (2019) aver that it is a recruitment tool, especially for advertising job vacancies and receiving applications. Beyond this, however, some employers and recruitment agencies have gone a step further to use social media to conduct initial interviews of candidates or for the first stage of the screening process, underscoring the digitalization of human capital sourcing and management.

ii. Improve Learning

Schools and students have found social media as a convenient tool to receive impact and share knowledge. Research affirms that social media enhances students' learning (Williams, 2023). However, on the opposite, they are also perceived by some teachers and parents as distraction platforms that negatively influence students. But in today's digital world, the new media is playing a meaningful role in the communication of knowledge, especially at the higher levels, which is difficult or cannot be undermined, more so that there is hardly any media outlet devoid of negatives or abuse. Hence, when used the right way, social media would enhance students' learning journey, making it much easier for students and educators to connect as well aside from being imbued with e-commerce gains in the global knowledge industry.

iii. Enhance Skills Acquisition

The potential of social media for engendering skills acquisition for economic empowerment is another associated strength. Through social media platforms, users learn new skills, and in some instances, improve existing skills by

collaborating with others, particularly colleagues in a given field. Moreover, there are sites for professionals like health practitioners, lawyers, teachers, media workers, and writers, where indeed career groups members interact to exchange ideas, explore new skills and knowledge for mutual growth and forums offering ample opportunities for economic empowerment through improved knowledge and skills (Onyejelem, et al, 2021).

Aside from users' skills development, social media also help in the grooming of a competent workforce for society, as an ancillary and human resource development mechanism for nations. Thus, individual users are empowered to build their wealth and improve their living standards alongside increasing society's degree of productivity and competitive capacity.

iv. Facilitate E-services

One of the biggest innovations presented by the digital age is the sophisticated widespread and diverse electronic banking products and services. Industries have evolved ways of using social media to initiate and complete their full business circle. For instance, banks and many financial service firms deploy Twitter or WhatsApp to facilitate account opening, all forms of withdrawals and transfers, with minimal or no manual input. Also, in the banking industry where customer interaction is necessary, digital media is becoming a strong communication channel between financial institutions and customers.

While Ram (2021) maintains that social networks provide opportunities for banks, customer services, and products and services, in Nigeria, Nwabueze, and Egbra, (2021) (cited in Ackland and Tanaka 2021) posit that it plays a crucial positive role in achieving microfinance banking goals by facilitating information flow to the poor and small business owners who are their major target. As such, Banks deploy social networks to inform customers about their products, upgrade and interact or interface with them at the same time. Meanwhile, not only the banking sector uses social media but virtually all business outfits, projecting them as economically significant platforms.

v. Mediums of Marketing and Advertising

Business marketing or product advertising (persuasive messages aimed to lure consumers to purchase products or services based on their worth) is fast becoming more of an online affair than the conventional offline in which social media have taken center stage. And as a result, there has been an increase in their usage even the smallest of businesses can now create awareness of the products and services they offer. It allows buyers and sellers to connect at little or no cost, becoming a new vista of marketing and advertising opportunities in the contemporary digital world.

Nonetheless, only those that effectively employ them can improve their business growth and profitability, thereby optimizing the digital media's inherent strength as a fortune-changing business information outlet, transmitted at the speed of light to people around the world. Ram (2020) asserts that both businesses and consumers are using the media not to share information, exchange opinions, and offer recommendations only but also to display certain consumption behaviours. It suggests that social media provides an avenue for not only data gathering on consumers' behaviour but product or service satisfaction feedback from the end-users as well.

6. Nigeria's Digital Economy Strength, Weaknesses and the Social Media

There is hardly any nation without its potential – social, economic, and cultural amongst others. In terms of the digital economy, this section takes a long look at factors that stand to place her at a vantage position as well as limiting full exploitation. This is undertaken about employing the social media avenue to catalyze a virile and sustainable digital economic development trajectory.

i. Geography and Population

One of the significant features of Nigeria is its geographical spread and large populace. Both often accord the country a prominent place and recognition in the regional and global socio-economic discourse because of the accompanying benefits aside from her natural and human resources endowment. With over 200 million population, constituting 47 percent of the West African sub-region, and 30 percent of which are youth (Pantami, 2020), the chance is strong to be one of the top-ten global digital economic driven nations.

However, some besetting challenges have been identified to be vitiating the translation of this strength into reality. These include poor internet access and penetration (World Bank, 2019), disparities of internet usage within the country based on region (south and north with the latter having low connection), urban and rural areas – with low connection in the rural areas, and employment, market size, access to electricity and gender (having age 60 and above disadvantaged) (Adeleke, 2020).

Based on these national predicaments, the geospatial and human population conferred catalytic power to deepen the digitalized economy is incapacitated for optimum positive yielding. Therefore, harnessing the useful youthful

population for intensive and extensive social media engagement in the digital world of commerce, skill acquisition, and employment would largely remain elusive, and digital economic diversification (articulated in the national digital economy policy and strategy 2020-2030, (Federal Ministry of Communication and Digital Economy, 2019) aspiration a mirage.

ii. Technology and Innovation

As established, technology is the key driver of social media. Moreover, Chiemeké and Imafidor (2020) submit that there exists a strong correlation between technology and productivity, making its availability an impetus to national economic growth. Furthermore, a disconnect between technology and innovation is difficult because of the rapid succession experience of innovation in the world today. The low-tech clearly characterized Nigeria as the least developed economy, implying a low capacity for not just innovation but also the exploitation of the social media potential.

Given the above condition, the country's effective engagement of the digital world to catalyze its economic growth appears limited. This is very vital, requiring an urgent reversal because the digital economic sub-sector positives cannot be harnessed from a weak point. And since social media connections through mobile phones and other similar technological devices, encouraging its availability and local innovative production would certainly enlarge the national value chain.

iii. Political and Economic Governance

Electronic governance of both the political and economic sectors of nations has been enabled by the online platforms of the internet, social media, and customized application packages. In Nigeria, some sectors such as customs services, public services – education, Inland revenue service (tax services), and national identification number registration amongst others – have been digitalized. As such, the public transacts business with minimal physical contact with the government. This is easing the cost of governance and increasing and securing public revenue sources. International Finance Corporation (IFC) (2019) asserts that the advent of the digital economy is fast-tracking the growth of Nigeria's economy.

In addition, the state is making efforts to expand the scope of the country's digital platform for increased benefits. For, instance, the European Union (EU) has signed a deal of 820 million Euros (160 and 660 as grants and loans respectively) to aid the transformation of Nigeria's digital sector, of which 2 million is aimed to improve public administration capacity (Global Gateway, 2022). It is expected that the EU partnership would impact both the private and public sectors of the economy. Additionally, Nigeria's economy is being rebased with digital economic activities to capture the current realities and expand the GDP (Edun, 2025). Implicitly, the digital sector has made significant contributions or serve as catalyst to economic development hitherto not statistically captured aside from other accompanied benefits its inclusion in the GDP can offer such as attraction of foreign investors.

While this portrays a progressive and strategic movement to engendering a digital economy by the government, the security of the system needs to be better hyped to win both the local and international users' interests. As well, awareness should be strengthened via social media massive publicity which affords opportunities for wider reach. In this regard, the tie between social media and the digital economy is revealed and positioned for optimum exploitation, more importantly, that of harvesting higher revenue from the social media firms, network providers, and users' direct and indirect taxation respectively.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper's objective is to determine the realistic nexus between social media and digital economic growth in Nigeria. The critical appraisal of the country's engagement of social media alongside that of the digital economy's strengths and weaknesses reveals that the active number of the population using social media is limited by constraints of limited internet penetration by citizens and together with a high cost of acquiring the technology. These, in consequence, are circumventing the optimum exploitation of the vast geographical space, population, and other locational advantages at the disposal of the country.

Also, the challenges impose limitations on harnessing the gains of skills acquisition, employment opportunities, recruitment facilitation, e-service or commerce promotion, increased revenue generation, and other benefits of an effective social media platform deployment. As such, this is oblique to the assumptions of the social media engagement theory that users' engagement would expand, prosper and facilitate feedback (Di Gandi and Wasco, 2016), weakening the prospect of digital economic development in Nigeria.

To mitigate the challenges above, the study recommends that Nigeria's government should intentionally promote, by incentivizing through tax rebates or holidays, more private sector investors in the information and

communication industry (ICT) (internet and technology production). This would not only domesticate production to generate employment and skills acquisition but reduce service costs also. Besides, the multilateral partnership with the EU needs to be exploited to improve citizens' digital engagement with consequent effects on digital economic activities while other bilateral and multilateral opportunities for homegrown technology development should be seized, especially via linkage programmes with Nigeria's university, technical schools and other skill acquisition institutes as well. Additionally, the government should intensify efforts to ramp up digital environment conduciveness and also increase investment in soft infrastructure such as satellites to facilitate seamless migration to higher broadband like 5G trending currently.

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